

Effect of nanoparticle and aggregate size on the relaxometric properties of MR contrast agents based on high quality magnetite nanoparticles

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ABSTRACT

Colloidal dispersions of monodispersed and high-crystalline magnetite nanoparticles have been used to establish a relationship between magnetic properties and MR relaxometric parameters in vitro. Magnetite nanoparticles with diameters between 4 and 14 nm were synthesized by thermal decomposition of Fe(acac)₃ in different organic solvents and transformed to hydrophilic by changing oleic acid for dimercaptosuccinic acid (DMSA). A final treatment in alkaline water was critical to make the suspension stable at pH 7 with ξ -potential values of -45 mV and hydrodynamic sizes as low as 50 nm. Samples showed superparamagnetic behaviour at room temperature, which is an important parameter for biomedical applications. Susceptibility increased with both particle and aggregate size, and for particles larger than 9 nm, was the aggregate size the key factor controlling the susceptibility. Relaxivity values followed the same trend than the suspension susceptibilities, indicating that the aggregate size is an important factor above a certain particle size governing the proton relaxation times. The highest relaxivity value, $r_2=317 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$, much higher than those for commercial contrast agents with similar hydrodynamic size, was obtained for a suspension consisting of 9 nm particles and 70 nm of hydrodynamic size and it was assigned to the higher particle crystallinity in comparison to particles prepared by coprecipitation. Therefore, it can be concluded that in addition to the sample crystallinity, both, particle size and aggregate size should be considered in order to explain magnetic and relaxivity values of a suspension.

KEYWORDS: Iron oxide, nanoparticles, MR contrast agents, DMSA, ligand exchange, relaxivity, magnetic colloidal suspensions, magnetic properties.

BRIEFS: Effect of nanoparticle and aggregate size on the relaxometric properties of MR contrast agents based on high quality magnetite nanoparticles

Introduction

MRI (Magnetic Resonance Imaging) is a non-invasive technique based on the variation of the water proton relaxation time from one tissue to another^{1,2}. The advantages of this technique are the use of non-ionizing energy and the high spatial resolution. Its major limitation is the sensitivity³⁻⁵ but it can be enhanced by the use of chemical compounds as contrast agents, that shorten the proton relaxation time, either the longitudinal (T1) or/and the transversal (T2) component. T1 agents, such as gadolinium or manganese chelates, give a bright positive contrast in T1-weighted sequence images⁶⁻¹⁰, whereas T2 agents, like superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles, give a dark negative contrast when a T2-weighted sequence is employed¹¹. The large magnetization of iron oxides can be a significant advantage in applications where a strong T2-effect is desired, for example in some cardiovascular applications.

Superparamagnetic iron oxide nanoparticles have been used as T2 contrast agent to detect injuries or deficiencies in liver¹², spleen¹³, lymph nodes^{14,15} and bone marrow¹⁶ because of the ability of the macrophages of the reticulo endothelial system (RES) to uptake them¹⁷. Actually commercial T2 contrast agents are iron oxide nanoparticles synthesized by coprecipitation and coated by different polymers or molecules¹⁶. Hydrodynamic size and coating, determine the nanoparticle biodistribution and the desired organ or tissue to be imaged^{4,18}. For example iron oxide nanoparticles coated by dextran (Feridex®, Guerbet) or carboxidextran (Resovist®, Schering) with a high hydrodynamic size have been used to image the liver^{19,20}. However, magnetic nanoparticles coated by the same polymers but with a low hydrodynamic size (Sinerem®, Guerbet and Supravist®, Schering) have been used as blood pool agents to image macrophages or lymph nodes²¹.

There are two different strategies to improve the quality of the contrast agents. One is related to the nanoparticle synthesis method and the other is related to the coating and the hydrodynamic size. Coprecipitation method presents several problems like the poor control of the size and size distribution and the lack of crystallinity of these particles due the presence of defects in the structure and lack of symmetry of the iron ions at the surface¹⁶. As a consequence of that, these nanoparticles present poor

magnetic properties which are in detriment of the contrast in the MR images. Uniform and high crystalline magnetite nanoparticles would be highly desirable for this application. In relation to the coating and the hydrodynamic size, an important effort should be done to developed contrast agents with covalently bonded ligands and small hydrodynamic sizes to enhance the blood half life time. Polymers or small molecules are usually bonded to the nanoparticle surface by adsorption forces and when the particles are introduced to the body they are desorbed due to dilution facilitating its aggregation and uptake by the macrophages¹⁶. The difficulty of having well control and well characterized magnetic nanoparticles and dispersions precludes the establishment of a clear relationship between nanoscale material characteristics and MR signal enhancement.

In this work, magnetic nanoparticles were synthesized by decomposition in organic media²²⁻²⁵, which assured the formation of uniform and highly crystalline magnetic nanoparticles, and therefore with enhanced magnetic properties, such as saturation magnetization values near the bulk^{26,27}. Water stability was attained by ligand exchange with dimercaptosuccinic acid (DMSA), which has been previously reported to provide high stability in aqueous media and free ligand groups for further biomolecule conjugations²⁸⁻³². We focused on the study of the structural, magnetic and colloidal properties of magnetic nanoparticles from its synthesis in organic media to its dispersion in aqueous colloidal suspensions, at pH 7, with the same iron concentration and hydrodynamic sizes lower than 100 nm. The evaluation of the suspensions as contrast agents was done by measuring the magnetic behaviour and the longitudinal and transverse proton relaxation times and the results were related to particle and aggregate size.

Several studies on uniform magnetic nanoparticles prepared by decomposition in organic media have already shown the effect of the particle size, nature and coating on the relaxivity parameters²⁸⁻³². In most cases, hydrodynamic size was not reported or the origin of the given values was unclear.

Experimental Section

Nanoparticles Synthesis. Magnetite nanoparticles of different sizes were synthesized by thermal decomposition of $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ in the presence of oleic acid and oleylamine as surfactants, and organic solvents with different boiling points³³.

The smallest particles were synthesized using phenyl ether as solvent (sample APh). The general preparation method is as follows: A mixture of 5.32 g $\text{Fe}(\text{acac})_3$ (15 mmol), 16.93 g 1,2-dodecanediol (75 mmol), 14.19 g oleic acid (45 mmol), 17.27 g oleylamine (45 mmol), and 150 mL phenyl ether was introduced into a four-necked flask and heated up to 200°C for 120 min with magnetically stirring and under a nitrogen flow. Then, the solution was heated to reflux (b.p. 254 °C) for 30 min in a N_2 atmosphere. To remove impurities, the solution at room temperature was mixed with ethanol, centrifuged at 5650 g for 10 min and the supernatant discarded. Finally, nanoparticles were mixed with 40 ml of hexane and 0.1 ml of oleic acid, and centrifuged twice at 5650 g 10 min. Pure and stable hydrophobic magnetite suspensions were obtained in all cases. Following a similar procedure, nanoparticles with larger sizes were obtained by using benzyl ether (sample ABz, b.p. 298 °C), trioctylamine (sample AOn, b.p. 365 °C) and 1-octadecene (sample AOc, b.p. 320 °C) as solvents. Powders from these suspensions were obtained by precipitation with ethanol and dryness at room temperature under a N_2 flow. It should be emphasized that this method can be scaled up to large production³⁴.

Surface modification. Ligand exchange reaction of oleic acid for dimercaptosuccinic acid (DMSA) was used to transform hydrophobic magnetite nanoparticles into hydrophilic, following a reported procedure^{28,29}. First, particles were coagulated from the hydrophobic suspension (50 mg/5 ml) by adding ethanol, centrifugation (2825 g, 10 minutes) and elimination of the solution. Then, a mixture of 25 ml toluene and a solution of 90 mg DMSA in 5 ml DMSO (dimethyl sulfoxide) were added to the coagulated particles, sonicated for five minutes and mechanically stirred during 24 hours. After that, toluene was added to the mixture reaction, centrifuged again and the supernatant containing the oleic acid coated particles discarded. Finally, the precipitated nanoparticles were successively mixed and centrifuged with ethanol and acetone several times to remove free oleic acid molecules.

A new final step was introduced in the surface modification process that consisted on the dispersion of the nanoparticles in alkaline water before its re-dispersion at pH 7. After that, the dispersion was dialyzed, its pH adjusted to 7 and, finally filtered by a 0.2 μm pore size syringe. Hydrophilic samples APhS, ABzS, AOnS and AOcS were named after the corresponding hydrophobic samples APh, ABz, AOn and AOc. Both, hydrophilic powders obtained by filtration and hydrophilic suspensions in water and agar, were analyzed in this work.

Characterization techniques. Particles were imaged in a 200-KeV JEOL-2000 FXII transmission electronic microscope to determine the mean particle size, polydispersity and shape. To prepare the samples for this technique, one drop of a dilute suspension of magnetite nanoparticles in either diethyl ether or acetone was placed on a carbon coated copper grid and allow to dry slowly at room temperature. Mean particle size was calculated from TEM data obtained by measuring the largest internal dimension of at least 300 particles. Data were fitted to a log-normal distribution and the parameters D_{TEM} (mean size) and P (polydispersity degree=standard deviation/mean size) were obtained from the fitting.

The X-ray diffractograms were collected between 10-80 (2θ) degrees in a X'Pert PRO (Panalytical) diffractometer using $\text{CuK}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda=1.5406 \text{ \AA}$). This technique provides information about the nanoparticle iron oxide phase and its crystal size (D_{XRD}). D_{XRD} was calculated from the broadening of the (311) reflection of the spinel structure following standard procedures³⁵.

Fourier transform infrared spectra were recorded between 3600 and 400 cm^{-1} in a NICOLET 20 SXC FTIR. Samples were prepared by diluting the iron oxide powder in KBr at 2% by weight and pressing it into a pellet. FTIR spectroscopy provides information about the coating molecules and therefore the effectiveness of the ligand exchange reaction. Moreover, FTIR provides information about iron oxide phase and the oxidation extent in the case of magnetite nanoparticles^{36,37}.

Magnetic characterization of powder samples (hydrophobic and hydrophilic) and hydrophilic suspensions solidified with agar (5% weight) was carried out in a vibrating sample magnetometer (MLVSM9 MagLab 9 T, Oxford Instrument) at room temperature. Interactions between aggregates can be neglected because the volume fraction was always very low. Magnetization curves were recorded by

first saturating the sample in a field of 5 Tesla; then, the saturation magnetization (M_s), and the coercive field (H_c) were determined for each sample. M_s values were evaluated by extrapolating to infinite field the experimental results obtained in the high field range, where magnetization linearly increases with $1/H$. Using the low field and high field portions of the room temperature magnetization curves, a magnetic particle size (D_{Mag}) has been obtained using Chantrell's equations³⁸ (equation 1), derived for non-interacting magnetic nanoparticles and assuming a log-normal distribution of particle sizes³⁹:

$$D_{Mag} = \left[\frac{18 k_B T}{\pi M_s} \sqrt{\frac{\chi_i}{3 m_i} \frac{1}{H_0}} \right]^{1/3} \quad (1)$$

m_s and M_s are the saturation magnetisation of the nanoparticles and the bulk phase respectively, χ_i is the initial susceptibility calculated at low field, in the region where the variation of M against H is linear, and $1/H_0$ is obtained by extrapolating M to 0 at high fields, in the region where the relationship between M and $1/H$ is a straight line.

Hydrodynamic size and polydispersity degree, and evolution of the zeta potential versus pH were evaluated for the hydrophilic suspensions in a ZETASIZER NANO-ZS device (Malvern Instruments). These parameters are important to characterize the nanoparticle size in solution and surface charge as a function of pH. Hydrodynamic size was measured at pH 7 and the intensity data were analyzed to obtain the Z-average size (Cumulants mean) and the intensity, volume and number distributions. Hydrodynamic size can be evaluated from the Z-average size or as the mean value of a distribution by intensity, volume or number. In dynamic light scattering (DLS), Z-average size is the most appropriate number produced by this technique to measure the hydrodynamic diameter of nanoparticles in solution and this is the number required for quality control purposes. In contrast to that number distribution, which could be 10 times smaller than the Z-average size, is of little use as small errors in gathering data from the correlation function will lead to huge errors in distribution by number⁴⁰. ξ -potential was measured in the same apparatus with 0.01 M concentration of KNO_3 at different pH values between 2 and 12.

Elemental analysis of the hydrophilic suspensions was carried out in a plasma emission spectrometer (ICP) PERKIN ELMER OPTIMA 2100 DV to measure the Fe concentration and to determine the coating percentage. Samples were digested with nitric acid to oxidize the organic coating and then with hydrochloride acid to dissolve the iron.

Relaxation time measurements were carried out in a MINISPEC MQ60 (Bruker) at 37 °C and a magnetic field of 1.5 T in order to evaluate the efficiency of the hydrophilic suspensions as contrast agents. The preparation of the samples involves the solidification of the hydrophilic suspensions with agar (5 %) as the samples preparation for magnetic characterization. The relaxation rates $R_{1,2}$ ($1/T_{1,2}$, s^{-1}) values were obtained from the relaxation times ($T_{1,2}$, s), and converted to relaxivities ($r_{1,2}$, $s^{-1}mM^{-1}$) by subtracting the agar contribution and dividing by the Fe concentration, according to equation 2.

$$R_{1,2} = R_{1,2}^o + r_{1,2} \cdot [Fe] \quad (2)$$

where $R_{1,2}^o$ (s^{-1}) is the relaxation rate in the absence of contrast agent and $[Fe]$ is the contrast agent concentration (mM). The constant of proportionality is the relaxivity $r_{1,2}$ ($s^{-1} mM^{-1}$) and is related to the proton relaxation rate per unit of contrast medium concentration.

Results and Discussion

Magnetic Nanoparticles. Nanoparticles of four different sizes (from 4 nm to 14 nm of average size) and narrow-size distribution (Polydispersity degree < 0.20) were obtained by decomposition of the same iron precursor in different organic solvents³⁴. Morphological parameter and TEM images of the samples are shown in Table 1 and Figure 1, respectively. The nanoparticles consisted on mainly magnetite as it is shown by the X-ray diffractograms (Supporting information, S1). Crystalline sizes (D_{XRD}) calculated from Scherrer's equation varied from 5 to 18 nm, in good agreement with TEM size (D_{TEM}) indicating that each particle is a single crystal. Cell parameter and crystalline size of the nanoparticles are included in Table 1.

All samples in the powder form **showed superparamagnetic-like behaviour** at room temperature with saturation magnetization values increasing from 62 emu/g to 82 emu/g as the nanoparticle size

increased, as well as the initial magnetic susceptibility (Figure 2). The high saturation magnetization values compared to magnetite nanoparticles prepared by other methods^{26,41} account for the high crystalline character of these nanoparticles and the presence of oleic acid covalently linked to them, which avoids oxidation and diminishes the surface spin disorder^{36,42}.

The transference of the particles to water was carried out by ligand exchange of oleic acid for DMSA as followed by IR spectroscopy (Figure 3). Thus, as the oleic acid was substituted by DMSA at the nanoparticles surface, the intensity of the bands near 3000 cm^{-1} (C-H stretching modes) due to oleic acid decreased while a band at 2510 cm^{-1} (S-H bond stretching) and broad absorption bands at 1140 and 1000 cm^{-1} (S-CH bond rocking vibrations) due to the DMSA appeared.

After the reaction, particle size seems to be unaltered by TEM (Fig. 4) but the colour of the resulting aqueous suspension was fairly brown, indicating that a certain degree of oxidation had taken place during the ligand exchange reaction. Both, FTIR and X-ray diffraction data supported this result (Figures 3 and Supporting information, S2). The IR spectrum for the hydrophilic samples presented extra bands attributed to the oxidation of magnetite to maghemite³⁷ near the absorption bands at 600 and 400 cm^{-1} , which correspond to the Fe-O stretching modes of the magnetite spinel structure^{43,44}. According to this, X-ray diffraction peaks for the hydrophilic samples (ABzS) were slightly displaced to higher 2θ values than those for the hydrophobic samples (ABz), indicating a smaller unit cell as expected when changing from magnetite, 8.39 \AA , to maghemite, 8.33 or 8.35 \AA (Supporting information, S2).

Magnetic characterization of the hydrophilic powders at room temperature **showed superparamagnetic-like** behaviour independently on the particle size, with zero remanence and zero coercivity (Supporting information, S3). The slight oxidation of the magnetite particles during the ligand exchange reaction lead to a reduction between 5 and 10 % of the saturation magnetization, which is more significant for 4 nm particles. The saturation values goes from 77 to 60 emu/g of iron oxide as the particle size decreases (Table 2). **Initial susceptibility is higher for the hydrophilic powders than for the hydrophobic ones with the same particle size, suggesting the presence of magnetic interparticle**

interactions in the hydrophilic samples. Interactions in nanoparticulate systems have been shown to account for the effective anisotropy energy barrier increase^{45,46}.

Aqueous colloidal suspensions. The determination of the colloidal properties of the hydrophilic suspensions in terms of stability with pH, time and concentration was carried out. The hydrodynamic size (Z-average) and ξ -potential variation as a function of the pH are represented in figures 5 and 6, respectively.

Dynamic light scattering data showed that the hydrophilic samples are monomodals as the corresponding hydrophobic ones. The Z-average size increases from 10 nm for the hydrophobic suspensions up to values between 50 nm and 70 nm for the hydrophilic suspensions (16 and 23 nm in number value, respectively), always smaller than 100 nm which is important for intravenous and therefore in vivo applications (table 2 and Figure 5). The values of the hydrodynamic size calculated by number distributions suggest a large fraction of particles with very small size. **The polydispersity degree for all samples was around 0.25.** The aggregate formation takes place due to the dipolar interaction between the particles and the shortening of the interparticle distance due to the change of oleic acid by a shorter ligand. A schematic representation of the aggregate structure in the suspensions is shown in figure 7 and the number of particles per aggregate going from 2500 to 35 as the particle size increases is included in Table 2.

On the other hand, the ξ -potential of the water-stable suspensions was negative in the whole pH range for all samples (Figure 6). At pH 7, the surface charge calculated from the ξ -potential data was around -40 mV. Please note that the isoelectric point for bare magnetite nanoparticles is around pH 7³⁷. In this case, the DMSA molecules provided the stabilization in water at pH 7 via electrostatic repulsions through the negative charge of the carboxylic groups that seems to be unfolded towards the solution.

A final treatment in alkaline water seemed to be critical to obtain a long time stability suspension. If water at pH 7 was directly used after ligand exchange to redisperse the powder, the suspension became unstable, hydrodynamic sizes increased with time up to 600 nm and flocculated in few minutes (data not shown). However, if particles were re-dispersed in a dilute NaOH solution, the suspension became

transparent with a reduction of the hydrodynamic size below of 100 nm and it was stable for months at any pH between 3 and 11. This result can be explained considering the DMSA chemistry^{47,48}. The DMSA is a small molecule and has a great capacity to complex metallic ions by using one or two of its carboxylic groups. When nanoparticles were dispersed in water at pH 7, the suspension was unstable because both carboxylic groups were bonded to the nanoparticles surface in a conformation displayed in figure 8 and there were no functional groups to make the suspensions stable. On top of that, thiol groups were pointed outside and could form disulfur bonds between particles helping with the suspension instability. However, when nanoparticles were dispersed in alkaline water, a spontaneous process occurred and one of the two carboxylic groups unlinked from the nanoparticle surface and was free to the solution. In this conditions, the carboxylic groups (COOH) transformed to carboxilates (COO⁻) and provided enough negative charge to stabilize the colloids via electrostatic repulsion in agreement with the ξ -potential data (Figure 6). Similar results were obtained by adsorbing DMSA at acid pH on magnetic nanoparticles prepared by coprecipitation^{49,50}. However in that case, an important quantity of Fe(II) was released into de medium due to the oxidation of the thiol-containing ligand at low pH.

Magnetic versus relaxometric properties. A relationship between the magnetic behaviour and the relaxometric properties have been analyzed for these samples. For that purpose, suspensions were solidified by adding agar into the aqueous media to fix the microstructure dispersion, avoiding possible alterations by the presence of a magnetic field.

Hydrophilic suspensions in agar were also superparamagnetic at room temperature (Figure 9) and the initial susceptibility increased as the nanoparticles size increased from 4 to 9 nm for samples with similar aggregate size (Figure 5). The sample consisting of 14 nm particles presented a lower initial susceptibility in spite of having the largest particle diameter but smaller aggregate size (Table 1). This result agrees with Chantrell et al data for ferrofluids^{38,49}. They claimed that when the interactions are weak, the reduced susceptibility is enhanced, however, above a certain diameter, initial susceptibility does not follow a Curie-Weiss law because the interactions are stronger and the initial susceptibility decreases. Magnetic diameter calculated from the magnetization curves of the suspensions in agar using

Chantrell's equation (eq. 1) shows a decrease from 9.1 (AOnS) to 8.0 nm (AOcS) when the particle size of the suspensions increase from 9 to 14 nm. This result supports the fact that interactions between particles are very strong within the aggregates above a certain particle size and control the initial susceptibility. Similar results measuring ac susceptibility have been found in biological tissues where particles were heterogeneously distributed leading to aggregates with obvious intra-aggregate interactions but negligible inter-aggregate interactions⁵¹.

Finally, the study of the relaxometric properties was carried out by measuring the proton relaxation time values (T1 and T2) against the iron concentrations (Figure 10). A linear dependence was found between the inverse of the relaxation times and the iron concentration for each sample, according to equation 2. Values of r_1 between $7 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$ for APhS and $19 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$ for AOcS were measured (Table 2), of the same order than those for commercial samples¹⁶ and other iron oxide superparamagnetic nanoparticles synthesized by decomposition⁵²⁻⁵⁴. It is clear from Figure 10 that as the nanoparticle size increased, the longitudinal proton relaxation time decreased and therefore r_1 increased. Similar variation with size was observed for T2 data for samples APhS, ABzS and AOnS (figure 10). Values of r_2 increased from 84 to $317 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$ as the particle size increased from 4 to 9 nm (Fig. 5). However, r_2 for sample AOcS was lower than expected according to its larger particle size ($204 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$) but agree well with its lower aggregate size. It should be mentioned that when the aggregate size of the suspensions of 4 and 14 nm particles is increased up to 200 nm, r_2 values increased up to 315 and $437 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$, respectively, as well as the susceptibility, showing the important effect of aggregation in both, the magnetic and the relaxometric properties of iron oxide nanoparticle suspensions. The aggregate itself can be considered as a magnetized sphere, where intercrystal interactions produce a high magnetic field gradient and consequently a dominant r_2 effect⁵⁵. Low r_1 and high r_2 values suggest that the main contribution to the relaxivity constant is the susceptibility effect⁶. The fact that particles are not uniformly distributed in the media because they are forming aggregates creates magnetization differences in a local area. This inhomogeneous distribution gives rise to local field gradients that

accelerate the loss of phase coherence of the spins contributing to the MR signal and producing an enhancement of r_2 .

The relaxivity values from the suspensions prepared in this work were as high as those reported for T2 agents based on DMSA coated ferrite nanoparticles²⁸. In that work it was shown that an increase in the magnetic nanoparticle size lead to an increase in the relaxivity, which agrees with our results. Furthermore, for the same particles size (12 nm), DMSA coated MnFe_2O_4 had the highest r_2 values, $350 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$, while Fe_3O_4 or Co and Ni ferrite had lower r_2 values, 218, 172 and $150 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$ respectively²⁹. Unfortunately, no data on the hydrodynamic size or magnetic properties of any sample was reported on these works and therefore, the origin of the contrast enhancement was unclear.

The contrast enhancement produced by nanoparticles synthesized by thermal decomposition had been assigned to the high crystallinity of the as-synthesized nanoparticles^{56,57}, although only the effect of clustering on the contrast enhancement was shown, in agreement with the results obtained for nanoparticles aggregated in micelles^{56,57}. Thus, particles prepared by this method with small hydrodynamic sizes, 15-30 nm, presented r_2 values of the order of $25\text{-}70 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$ ^{31,54,56}, similar to Sinerem or Combidex, commercial products prepared by coprecipitation with hydrodynamic sizes of 30 nm at the same field strength (1.5 Tesla). However, when the hydrodynamic size of the particles prepared by thermal decomposition was above 200 nm, relaxivity values increased up to $150 \text{ s}^{-1}\text{mM}^{-1}$ ³⁰, similar to the value obtained for Endorem with 150 nm of hydrodynamic size. In contrast to that, our sample consisting of 9 nm particles with a hydrodynamic size of 70 nm showed 1.5 times higher relaxivity than Resovist, prepared by coprecipitation with similar hydrodynamic size¹⁶, showing the importance of particle crystallinity. Values of r_2/r_1 , which are also indicative of the effectiveness of the contrast agent, were very high for the 9 nm sample ($r_2/r_1=17$), similar to Resovist and much higher than the value reported for Sinerem ($r_2/r_1=7$).

It can be concluded that for the development of new advanced contrast agents, highly crystalline magnetic nanoparticles would be desirable as those prepared in this work. It has been observed that magnetic behaviour and proton relaxation time of the suspensions are strongly determined by

nanoparticle and hydrodynamic size in solution. At 1.5 Tesla, r_2 values increased as the saturation magnetization increased as a consequence of the particle size increase. However, samples with large particle size showed similar saturation magnetization but different r_2 values due to the different aggregate size, which affects the initial susceptibility values at low field.

Conclusions

In summary, aqueous colloidal suspensions of uniform and highly crystalline magnetite nanoparticles with sizes between 4 nm and 14 nm have been prepared by thermal decomposition in organic media and dimercaptosuccinic acid (DMSA) ligand exchange reaction. The ligand exchange reaction with DMSA was found to be an easy, rapid, effective and highly reproducible method to transfer oleic acid capped magnetite nanoparticles to an aqueous media leading to suspensions with hydrodynamic sizes smaller than 100 nm. A final alkalization step in the ligand exchange reaction seems to be crucial to obtain stable suspensions at pH 7 with high negative surface charge due to carboxylic groups unbonded toward the suspension. T1 and T2 measurements show that these suspensions have a very promising future as MR contrast agents because of its high relaxivity with low hydrodynamic size. According to the magnetization curves at room temperature, saturation magnetization and susceptibility of the suspensions are key factors to control r_2 values. Thus, when the suspensions are formed by nanoparticles of small sizes, r_2 increases with size when the aggregate size is similar but above a certain size, the aggregate size is the factor that prevails for determining r_2 . Finally, it can be concluded that SPIO particles synthesized by decomposition in organic media clearly show significant advantages over the commercially available iron oxide particles.

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Table 1. Morphological, structural and magnetic properties of hydrophobic magnetite nanoparticles with different sizes. Ms values are normalized to grams of iron oxide.

sample	D_{TEM} (nm)	P (%)	D_{XRD} (nm)	cell parameter (Å)	%weight coating	magnetic properties				
						5K		RT		
						m_s (emu/g)	H_c (Oe)	m_s (emu/g)	χ_{ini} (emu/g·T)	D_M (nm)
APh	3.8	20	5.1	8.37	19.3	79	275	62	390	5.2
ABz	6.4	12	7.3	8.39	15.7	84	330	73	643	6.2
AOn	9.2	13	11.9	8.39	7.5	87	320	75	1876	7.5
AOc	14.2	11	18.5	8.38	7.1	89	490	82	2258	10.1

Table 2. Colloidal and MR relaxometric properties of magnetite aqueous suspensions from hydrophilic nanoparticles with different sizes. Ms values are normalized to grams of iron oxide.

sample	D_{TEM} (nm)	D_H (nm)	particles forming an aggregate	m_s (emu/g)	D_M^{Powder} (nm)	$D_M^{\text{Suspension}}$ (nm)	r_1 (mM ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	r_2 (mM ⁻¹ s ⁻¹)	r_2/r_1
APhS	3.8	65	2500	60	4,8	4,9	6.9	84	12
ABzS	6.4	65	680	68	5,5	6,8	7.4	116	16
AOnS	9.2	70	325	70	8,6	9,0	18.5	317	17
AOcS	14.2	50	35	77	9,7	8,0	18.8	204	11

nanoparticles with different sizes. Ms values are normalized to grams of iron oxide.

FIGURE CAPTIONS

Fig. 1 TEM images and size-distribution graphs for the hydrophobic nanoparticles (bar = 50 nm). The continuous line is the log-normal fitting function of the particle size data.

Fig.2 Magnetization curves at room temperature for the hydrophobic nanoparticles.

Fig. 3 Infrared spectra for a hydrophobic and a hydrophilic sample (ABz and ABzS).

Fig. 4 TEM images for the hydrophilic nanoparticles (bar = 50 nm)

Fig. 5 Hydrodynamic size, initial susceptibility and r_2 values as a function of the nanoparticle size for hydrophilic suspensions in agar.

Fig. 6 Evolution of the ξ -potential against pH for ABzS sample after alkaline treatment.

Fig. 7 Schematic representation of the aggregate structure in the suspensions.

Fig. 8 Possible structures of the DMSA molecules surrounding the iron oxide nanoparticles.

Fig. 9 Magnetization curves of the hydrophilic suspensions in agar at RT.

Fig. 10 Inverse of the relaxation times as a function of the iron concentration for hydrophilic suspensions in agar.

FIGURES

FIGURE 1

FIGURE 2

FIGURE 3

FIGURE 4

FIGURE 5

FIGURE 6

FIGURE 7

FIGURE 8

FIGURE 9

FIGURE 10